

THE LEVEL OF COLLEGE PREPAREDNESS OF GRADE 12 STUDENTS OF MAMALI NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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The Level of College Preparedness of Grade 12 Students of Mamali National High School

Mae Ann N. Tolentino,* Arsyl M. Andaya, Karen May P. Urlanda, Samantha R. Cuaresma,
Vincent Roi B. Butalan, Matrex A. Mamintal, Christal Ashly Valdez

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of college preparedness of grade 12 students of Mamali National High School. It also developed the students' profile, aspirations, and readiness to pursue a college degree. The study utilized the descriptive research design. The respondents of the study were the total population of Forty-nine (49) grade 12 students of Mamali National High School for the school year 2023-2024. The researchers adopted a survey questionnaire from Cuy and Salinas (2019) to determine the preparedness of grade 12 students. To give meaning to the data generated from the survey, the study utilized frequency count, percentage, weighted mean and correlation. Findings revealed that distribution of respondents in terms of Profile, aspiration and readiness has a significant relationship between respondents' profile and respondents level of college readiness. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommended: Parents and teachers should support students' high aspirations by providing them with necessary knowledge and skills for college education, Senior high school students should develop a strong academic foundation, enhance skills, develop critical thinking, manage time effectively, and improve communication skills for college readiness. And the study's limitations suggest future research should expand data collection and consider variables like expectations and academic preparedness for more accurate results.

Keywords: *college preparedness, college degree, college readiness*

Introduction

Education can promote social mobility and positively impact individuals' lives. It is a crucial part of a person's existence. It improves cognitive abilities and knowledge retention. Many students pursue further education to enhance their employment opportunities or prospects in the workforce. Making the transition from high school to college can be difficult, but it is an essential stage in the process of obtaining a college education.

In recent times, there has been a growing focus on the aspirations of individuals and how these affect their future actions. Students from diverse backgrounds may have high aspirations that don't necessarily correlate with their school performance. These aspirations, often expressed as hopes or desires, are relatively stable beliefs that encapsulate a part of an individual's future-oriented beliefs, preferences, and abilities.

In international studies, both academic and extracurricular accolades may influence college readiness. The study by Uy, Kim, and Khuon (2019) shows that college and career readiness of full-time Southeast Asian American college students in New England struggled to navigate to step up into college and did not feel prepared for a career. Khattab's (2019) research explores how aspirations, expectations, and academic performance influence students' future educational behavior. Research indicates that the financial benefits of having a college degree compared to a high school diploma are greater than ever. Some students lack the necessary attitudes or abilities to succeed in college, highlighting the importance of college readiness.

Nagaoka et al. (2013) stated that non-cognitive factors like behaviors, skills, attitudes, and strategies are as important as academic knowledge for success in college education. Being adequately prepared for college not only increases a student's chances of earning a degree but also reduces disparities in persistence and degree completion among different racial and income groups.

Understanding what it means to be "college ready" is crucial. Previous research on college readiness focused on individual-level indicators. College readiness is the academic and practical knowledge necessary for success in college education. Mueller and Lee (2013) identified factors contributing to a lack of college and career readiness, including academic readiness and preparedness, expected behavior and attitudes, and knowledge about college and career.

Locally, there has been an increasing recognition of the importance of college preparedness. Yet, there is still a lack of comprehensive studies focusing on the level of preparedness among the grade 12 students in Mamali National High School. This study aims to fill the gaps by providing an in-depth analysis of the preparedness level of students entering college.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of college preparedness of Grade 12 Senior High School students at Mamali National High School. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of Grade 12 students in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;

- 1.3. track; and
- 1.4. family income?
2. What is the level of college preparedness of Grade 12 students in terms of:
 - 2.1. aspiration; and
 - 2.2. readiness?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of student to the level of preparedness of the grade 12 student?

Literature Review

College readiness in terms of age

Age Not a Significant Factor: A study by Heo and Han (2019) found age itself doesn't significantly predict college readiness. However, the study did find that motivation and academic stress can influence a student's self-directed learning readiness (SDLR), which can be a factor in college success.

Middle School Influences Readiness: Gaertner and McClarty (2019) suggest factors beyond academics, like motivation and behavior developed in middle school (which coincides with ages 11-14), contribute to college preparedness. This highlights the importance of those middle school years for building a foundation for college success. While age might not be the sole indicator, the experiences a student has at different ages can influence the skills and behaviors that contribute to college readiness.

College readiness in terms of Gender

A study by You Science (2022) suggests females might lag behind in feeling prepared for college, despite potentially stronger academic performance. This points to a gap in exposure to career guidance and confidence-building initiatives, even if their grades are good. The study found: Less exposure to a variety of college and career options for females, lower rates of females talking to counselors about post-high school opportunities, and despite potentially higher GPAs, a lower percentage of females felt prepared to choose a major.

Other studies, like one from 2008-2009 examining Texas high school students, found girls had slightly higher college readiness in reading and language arts compared to boys. This might not be the case for all subjects, however. It's important to note that these studies don't paint the whole picture. There can be significant disparities within genders, particularly for students of color.

This report by SREE (2014) explores historical trends and research on gender and college readiness in the US. It highlights the need to consider factors like social capital and access to guidance resources alongside academic performance.

YouScience (2022), This study highlights a potential confidence gap for females despite their academic performance. It suggests they might receive less exposure to career guidance and opportunities compared to males. While not solely focused on gender, these reports offer valuable data on high school graduation rates, standardized test scores, and college enrollment trends disaggregated by gender. The Condition of Education (2023).

A study by Riegle-Crumb et al. (2016) examined the relationship between social-emotional learning (SEL) and college readiness, with a specific focus on gender. They found that for both genders, stronger social-emotional skills were associated with higher levels of college readiness. However, the study also suggested that interventions targeting these skills might be particularly beneficial for boys.

A study by Anthony and Rocci (2020) explored differences in STEM course selection (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math) between genders. They found that while girls were closing the gap in participation, there were still disparities in specific STEM fields like engineering and computer science. This could potentially impact their college readiness for those majors.

College readiness in terms of Track

Heo and Han (2019): This study in the Philippines found a correlation between senior high school tracks (akin to academic streams) and college readiness. Students in STEM tracks (Science, Technology, Engineering, Math) tended to score higher on college readiness assessments compared to those in non-STEM tracks.

Scirp (2014), this research looked at college readiness in the Philippines focusing on senior high school students. It found that students' perception of their own college readiness differed significantly based on their academic track. Those in STEM tracks felt more prepared compared to students in non-STEM tracks.

College readiness in terms of Family Income

The Education Trust (2017), this organization focused on educational equity found a correlation between family income and college readiness. Students from higher-income families tended to score higher on standardized tests, take more rigorous coursework in high school (like Advanced Placement classes), and have greater access to test prep resources. These factors can all contribute to college readiness.

College Board (2022), reported the highlights the financial challenges faced by low-income students. The rising cost of college can make it difficult for these students to afford college, even if they are academically prepared. This can create a barrier to college

readiness, even for qualified students.

ACT (2015) This study by the ACT examines college readiness specifically for students from low-income families. The study highlights how low-income students might have limited access to resources that can support college readiness, such as advanced coursework in high school, college counseling, and test preparation materials. Also, the financial burden of college can be a significant barrier for low-income students, even if they are academically prepared.

This can impact their ability to choose a college or complete their degree. And Students from low-income backgrounds may attend schools with fewer resources, potentially impacting their academic foundation and college preparedness. Furthermore, Factors like poverty-related stress and unstable housing can negatively impact a student's ability to focus on academics and prepare for college.

Level of college preparedness of Grade 12 students in terms of Aspiration

Cuy and Salinas (2019) stipulated that students are very positive and confident of their academic abilities and skills needed in college which also shows that they had clear aspiration of what they really wanted in pursuing college education. Furthermore, Mills, Lester, and Jones (2021) which disclosed that students are determined to enter college and persisted to graduate despite facing obstacles. Moreover, Toutkoushian (2018) that students increase and decrease their college aspirations over time, and such changes are strongly related to high school performance and family mobility. Lastly, The research of Abuyog & Madrona (2019) investigated the relationship between Grade 12 students' aspirations and their perceived college readiness in the Philippines. The study found that students with higher aspirations for college also demonstrated higher levels of self-reported college readiness. This suggests a positive association between a strong desire for college and taking steps to prepare for it.

A study by Hausmann et al. (2018) examined the role of academic aspirations in predicting college enrollment. The research found that students with higher academic aspirations during high school were more likely to enroll in college compared to those with lower aspirations. In addition, Nita & Ayu (2021) research, found a correlation between students' aspirations and perceived college readiness. The study emphasizes the importance of fostering aspirations to motivate students to seek resources and take initiative for college preparation. SREE (2014), While not directly focused on aspiration, this report by the Society for Research on Educational Effectiveness (SREE) explores gender disparities in college readiness in the US. It highlights the importance of considering social and economic factors alongside academic achievement. Even with strong aspirations, some students might face challenges due to limited access to quality education or guidance resources. Also, suggests that nurturing aspirations can be beneficial.

Level of college preparedness of Grade 12 students in terms of Readiness

Duckworth et al. (2019), states that high levels of self-discipline during adolescence were associated with a greater likelihood of obtaining a college degree and pursuing advanced education and students who set goals before entering college will most likely succeed in their college life. Van der Velden et al. (2020). Whereas, Paat et al (2020), stating that college readiness is not a monopoly of a single factor but a confluence of numerous interplaying factors.

Improving College Readiness in the Age of the Common Core (2017), this MDRC report examines the challenges of ensuring students graduate high school with the skills needed for college success. It highlights the need to measure college readiness beyond just standardized tests, focusing on skills like critical thinking, time management, and self-directed learning. The Condition of College and Career Readiness 2014: Students from Low-Income Families (2015), this ACT study examines college readiness specifically for low-income students. While the study uses ACT scores as a measure, it also acknowledges the importance of factors like access to rigorous coursework and college counseling in preparing students for college-level work.

Empowering College Readiness: Insights and Collaborations

College readiness refers to the set of skills, knowledge, and behaviors a graduating Senior High School student should have upon entering their freshmen year of college. Research about college readiness is beneficial not only to students but also to high schools preparing younger students and whether a college should accept a student. These studies and works helps the researchers in providing useful information with the assured authenticity to be served.

College Preparedness is a global topic. It is essential for a student know and to be exposed to the process of planning for college and for schools to help them, School counselors are often charged with ensuring the college and career readiness of all students (ASCA, 2012). In schools, Gysbers (2013) suggested that school counselors served students by providing activities that "support student planning by giving emphasis to the development and use of decision-making, goal setting, and planning skills" and by stressing "basic academic and career and technical education preparation skills.

Adults like teachers, professionals, and older students that has experienced the current situation of incoming college freshmen is also a part in influencing students' perceptions and plans in college. Connecting with batchmate in college preparations can also be effective. Mitra and Gross (2009) defined three types of student voice: being heard, collaborating with adults, and building capacity for leadership. Collaborating with adults has been occurring most frequently in schools by getting feedback from students after completing an assessment or parts of the course and asking for input in creating the lessons.

College readiness

College readiness is crucial for graduating Senior High School students, as defined by Greene (2019) of the Manhattan Institute. College readiness includes a regular diploma, completion of minimum course requirements, and basic reading skills. Federal policy can help communicate the need for college preparation and provide public information. The federal government should invest in research and development to support programs, provide funding for struggling high schools, and improve data collection and analysis. States should develop better student support policies, align them with academic rigor, develop high school models, improve data systems, and monitor and evaluate state policies to identify inconsistencies, implementation concerns, and technical assistance needs.

Preparedness of senior high school grade 12 students

The results of a 2021 research by Schnieders and Moore (2021), emphasized the differences in participation, pointing out that students enrolled in college credit courses and those exposed to in-person instruction were more likely to engage in such activities. Based on studies conducted by Vecaldo and Tamayo et al. The bulk of responders, according to the data, were ill-prepared for college. Furthermore, there were notable differences in the degree of readiness based on the kind of senior high school (SHS) from which they graduated and the SHS track and strand they had studied. According to Kendall's tau-b statistic results, IPs were more likely to be prepared for college if they had higher SHS grade point averages (GPAs), more awards, both academic and nonacademic, more involvement in extracurricular activities, and more participation in groups. In terms of instructional strategy, raising college readiness while taking the academic profile into account increases the likelihood that IPs will be accepted into universities and be able to succeed in foundational courses without the need for remediation.

College preparedness of grade 12 students

The primary element of transitional academic assistance within a particular program is examined by Heartfield (2023). The report also outlines the ways in which different precollege programming stakeholders encourage students' perseverance all the way to and through college. This qualitative study makes use of semi-structured interviews and a review of the program website in a single case study methodology. The resulting data provides examples of the culturally appropriate teaching, delivery strategies, and student support employed in the program. The results of this study demonstrate the significance of connections and teamwork in preserving academic readiness and culturally appropriate education. This study, which focuses on the opinions of after-school program designers and implementers, contributes to the expanding body of research on the relationships between after-school college preparation programs and postsecondary achievement (Tichavakunda, 2019).

Hardeman (2023) states that this study investigated sophomores at a private Christian university in the South's assessments of their preparedness for college. 42 participants provided information via an electronic questionnaire, which was used to look at three areas: the participants' perceived levels of preparation for college, the reasons they believed would affect their level of preparation, and the obstacles they saw in achieving their goals. Qualitative data were examined regarding each participant's choice of secondary education (public, private, or homeschooling). Though specific to the sort of secondary schooling attended, the areas of academics, time management, and personal accountability were shown to have the highest rated preparation. Additionally, specific to the sort of secondary education obtained, advanced academics, time management, academics, and personal accountability were judged to promote college readiness. Last but not least, time management, the environment, personal accountability, and academics were viewed as obstacles by all three groups.

The opinions of underprivileged adolescents and the educators who work with them on college and job preparedness were canvassed for this study, according to Lindstorm et al. Teenagers that have unequal access to educational resources are classified as underprivileged kids. 84 focus group participants a mix of educators and students were chosen through purposeful sampling (9–12th grade). Focus group data were analyzed using grounded theory, and the results fell into three main groups. First, in order to create particular postschool plans, students and educators defined preparedness as having certain professional knowledge and abilities. Second, instructors gave instances of difficult life situations that prevent young people from reaching their full potential in college and the workplace, and both students and instructors saw this as a barrier due to the lack of experiences available for job preparation. Third, instructors and students noted that giving young people access to a wide range of profession-related learning activities and having reliable adults present to function as mentors and advisors can help them explore more career alternatives.

Preparing high school students for college

Bernette et al. (2018) indicate that this study looks at 37 Texas state and local college preparedness partnership initiatives, along with the partnerships that brought these programs to life. The research and Texas policy literature were reviewed, an online search of Texas's college readiness partnership programs with a web presence was conducted, and site visits to high schools, colleges, and community-based organizations in the Houston and Dallas-Fort Worth regions were conducted to arrive at the conclusions. College preparation partnership programs are described by the authors as programmatic interventions that are co-sponsored by secondary and postsecondary institutions and made available to high school students with the aim of improving their preparedness for college.

According to Daiek et al. the number of underprepared students entering postsecondary education is increasing, with research showing that current developmental education is not effective in helping these students overcome their academic shortcomings. The growing

concern is that the educational system must now find ways to prepare the thousands of people who have lost their jobs unexpectedly and prepare high school students for college. Developmental education should encompass more than just remedial instruction, including college-level gateway courses, support services for nonremedial learners, and self-regulation skills for success in college. Comprehensive developmental education programs can address these educational difficulties and help students overcome academic shortcomings.

Financial support for grade 12 students

Levitz conducted a poll, according to Ruffalo, asking 1,250 high school students in the eleventh and twelfth grades about their plans to pay for college, how they learn about financial aid, and how they become interested in attending colleges and institutions. Key findings include: (1) 90% of students think it will be difficult to pay for college; (2) 57% of 11th-grade students have heard about financial aid; (3) Almost 80% of 12th grade students intend to borrow money; (4) First-generation students and those without family involvement require additional support; and (5) 71% of 12th grade students express interest in at least one new university. For the 2020 High School Student Perceptions of College Financing Report, the prior report.

This study by Tamayo et al. aims to address the lack of a standardized test for college readiness in the Philippines, aligning with the College Readiness Standards (CRS) established by the Philippine Commission on Higher Education (CHED). The test aims to address the disparate and arbitrary indices used by Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to gauge the readiness of Filipino K-12 graduates for college enrollment. The study validates the CRT's validity and reliability as a tool for assessing the abilities, knowledge, and reflective thinking required for K-12 graduates to succeed in General Education courses at HEIs without remediation. The 200-item CRT has a large functioning distractors, desirable difficulty index, and a reasonably good discrimination index. The study also found that the CRT has inter-item consistency, indicating its reliability. Its contextualized, gender-neutral, and criterion-referenced properties make it a reliable and trustworthy tool for assessing the college preparation of Filipino K-12 graduates.

Methodology

Research Design

The approach used in this quantitative research work was the descriptive-correlational survey method. According to Lappe (2000), a descriptive-correlational survey involves the observation and the collection of information on the two variables to establish a statistically corresponding relationship between them. The survey methodology of data collection was utilized and can obtain information from large samples of the population. This method is suited to gather demographic data that describe the composition of the model and the respondents that were specifically selected to represent the population (Glasow, 2005).

Respondents

The respondents of this study were Grade 12 Senior High School students in Mamali National High School. This study focused only on graduating students' preparedness for college education. A total of 61 respondents were chosen through a purposive sampling technique. Respondents were officially enrolled in Grade 12 for School Year 2023-2024. This study was conducted at Mamali National High School located at Mamali, Lambayong, Sultan Kudarat.

Mamali National High School, a prominent educational institution, is situated in Purok. Pagkakaisa, Mamali II, Lambayong Sultan Kudarat. The school's location, adjacent to Mamali National High School and opposite the Jazz Bar, is strategic accessible. The institution caters not only the educational needs of the youth but also extend its service to students from the neighboring barangays of Pidtiguian, Kulasi and Lumabao. The school offers both Junior and Senior High School curriculums, providing a comprehensive academic framework for its students. The physical infrastructure comprises 16 classrooms housed in 9 separate buildings, creating an environment conducive to effective learning. Additionally, the presence of 3 administrative offices ensures efficient management and support for the educational activities. Mamali National High School is dedicated to fostering an environment that promotes academic excellence and holistic development of its students.

Instrument

An adapted survey questionnaire from Cuy and Salinas (2019) was utilized in this study.

Procedure

An approved letter to conduct the study was secured from the Office of the School Principal. Upon the approval and request to conduct the study, the requirements of collecting data responses from the participants were considered. In disseminating the questionnaire, the researchers utilized allotted vacant and practical research time to avoid the disruption of classes. The researchers personally administered the survey questionnaire to the respondents. After answering the survey questionnaire, the retrieval of the questionnaire was done on the same day as the questionnaire was distributed. The researchers ensure that the instrument used was reliable and accurate for better interpretation of the data and other imperative information.

It is important to establish gathered information is accurate and proper. The data collected via the questionnaire was scored, recorded, and classified using statistical analysis. Data were analyzed and interpreted in accordance with the purpose of the study.

Data Analysis

The mean was utilized to compute the average set of values of the survey responses. An analysis of variance tested whether there is a statistically significant difference between the means of the groups or if the differences could have occurred by chance.

Results and Discussion

This part summarizes the outcomes of the information collected from respondents who were the Grade 12 students of Mamali National High School analyzes those results, and interprets them to address the issues raised by the study. The data were presented via tables, figures, and texts, and the explanation centered on the order of the questions in the problem statement in Chapter I.

Profile of the Grade 12 students in terms of Age, Gender, Track and Average Monthly Financial Income

The first research problem identified the student's demographic profile, including age, gender, track, and financial aspect. The table displays frequency counts and percentage distributions within specific categories.

Table 1. *Profile of Grade 12 students in College Preparedness among Grade 12 Students of Mamali National High School in terms of Age, Gender, Track and Average Monthly Financial Income*

INDICATORS	FREQUENCY COUNT	PERCENTAGE
AGE		
18-19	38	78%
20 Above	11	22%
TOTAL	49	
GENDER		
MALE	27	55%
FEMALE	22	45%
TOTAL	49	
TRACK		
COOKERY	18	37%
GAS	15	30%
ICT	16	33%
TOTAL	49	
FINANCIAL		
30k Above	6	12%
29,999-20,000	20	41%
19,999 below	23	47%
TOTAL	49	100%

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, track, and financial income. As reflected in Table 2, 78% of the respondents are aged 18-19 years old. 55% of respondents are male students. In terms of track, 37% of the respondents belong to Cookery, 33% are Information and Communication Technology, and 30% belongs to General Academic Strand. In terms of financial income, 47% of the respondents have 19,000 and below income.

Table 2. *College Preparedness among Grade 12 Students of Mamali National High School in terms of the Level of Aspiration in Pursuing College Degree*

INDICATORS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
1. Do well in school to fulfill my dream.	1.57	Not Affected
2. Enjoy my college years before assuming adult respondents.	1.76	Slightly Affected
3. Achieve a high general weighted average (GWA).	2.16	Moderately Affected
4. Decide on what career I want to pursue.	2.06	Slightly Affected
5. Explore new ideas	1.98	Slightly Affected
6. Acquire a well-rounded general education	2.08	Slightly Affected
7. Obtain a skill I need to pursue my chosen career.	2.02	Slightly Affected
8. Discover what kind of person I really want to be.	2.33	Slightly Affected
9. Consistently do my schoolwork well.	1.94	Slightly Affected
10. Do my best to achieve my goals.	2.18	Slightly Affected
11. Finish college regardless of obstacles.	1.14	Not Affected
12. Develop a personal code of values and ethics.	1.92	Slightly Affected
13. Be confident of my academic abilities	2.94	Moderately Affected
TOTAL	2.01	Slightly Affected

As disclosed in Table 2, most of the responses of the students in terms of level of aspiration in pursuing college degree of grade 12 students of Mamali National High School is Slightly Affected.

Specifically, the results show that Item number 13, Be confident of my academic abilities, attained the highest mean of 2.94 interpreted

as Moderately Affected. This implies that the confidence of the students on their academic abilities affects their aspiration to pursue college.

In agreement to this, Cuy and Salinas (2019) stipulated that students are very positive and confident of their academic abilities and skills needed in college which also shows that they had clear aspiration of what they really wanted in pursuing college education.

On the other hand, Item number 11, finish college regardless of obstacles, got the lowest mean of 1.14 interpreted as Not Affected. This means that obstacles and challenges do not affect the aspiration of the Grade 12 students in pursuing college degree.

This is supported by Mills, Lester, and Jones (2021) which disclosed that students are determined to enter college and persisted to graduate despite facing obstacles.

Overall, the College Preparedness among Grade 12 Students of Mamali National High School in terms of level of Aspiration in pursuing college degree attained an overall mean of 2.01 interpreted as Slightly Affected. This reveals that while aspiration plays a role, it has a relatively minor impact on the students' decision to pursue a college degree.

This result is in consonance with the study of Toutkoushian (2018) that students increase and decrease their college aspirations over time, and such changes are strongly related to high school performance and family mobility.

Table 3 shows the level of readiness in pursuing college degree among grade12 students of Mamali National High School.

As to the specifics, it can be viewed that Item number 8, I am self-disciplined (If something needs to be done, I do it in a timely manner), attained the highest mean of 3.88 interpreted as Highly Affected. This shows that self-discipline greatly affects the readiness in pursuing a college degree.

Table 3. *College Preparedness among Grade 12 Students of Mamali National High School in terms of Readiness in Pursuing College Degree*

INDICATORS	FREQUENCY COUNT	INTERPRETATION
1. I have clear college goals.	1.39	Not Affected
2. I can handle change well.	1.71	Not Affected
3. I am quick to get things done and self-motivated.	1.88	Slightly Affected
4. I take care of myself and can handle uncertainty.	1.80	Slightly Affected
5. I can manage my time well.	2.06	Slightly Affected
6. I have done some serious thinking about career options.	2.18	Slightly Affected
7. I have a distinct desire to be successful in college.	2.06	Slightly Affected
8. I am self-disciplined (If something needs to be done, I do it in a timely manner).	3.88	Highly Affected
9. I take responsibility for my decisions for I am a good decision maker.	1.96	Slightly Affected
10. I am optimistic about my future.	1.98	Slightly Affected
11. I set clear achievement goals for myself.	1.77	Slightly Affected
12. I can organize my time and things I need to do.	3.55	Highly Affected
13. I understand my academic strengths.	3.57	Highly Affected
14. I know the importance of not giving up and sticking through difficult tasks.	3.53	Highly Affected
15. I have an idea of what I want to do with my career.	3.53	Highly Affected
TOTAL	2.42	Slightly Affected

This is supported by the study of Duckworth et al. (2019), he states that high levels of self-discipline during adolescence were associated with a greater likelihood of obtaining a college degree and pursuing advanced education.

On the other hand, Item number 1, I have clear college goals, got the lowest mean of 1.39 interpreted as Not Affected. This suggests that the readiness of the students in entering college does not rely on having clear college goals.

This is in contradiction to Van der Velden et al. (2020), stating that students who set goals before entering college will most likely succeed in their college life.

Overall, the college preparedness of Grade 12 students in terms of their level of readiness in pursuing college degree got an overall mean of 2.42 interpreted as Slightly Affected. This indicates that while students may have some level of readiness, there are factors that slightly hinder their preparedness for college.

This view is supported by the study of Paat et al. (2020), stating that college readiness is not a monopoly of a single factor but a confluence of numerous interplaying factors.

The college preparedness of Grade 12 students in terms of Level of aspiration and readiness in pursuing college degree got an overall mean of 2.22 interpreted as Agree.

This indicates that they play a vital role in shaping Grade 12 students' preparation in entering college for us to become ready to step into the higher form of education, which is college.

Table 4. *The Summary of the College Preparedness in terms of the Level of Aspiration and Readiness in Pursuing College Degree*

INDICATORS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
2.1 Level of Aspiration in Pursuing College Degree	2.01	Slightly Affected
2.2 Level of Readiness in Pursuing College Degree	2.42	Slightly Affected
TOTAL	2.22	Slightly Affected

The research of Abuyog & Madrona (2019) investigated the relationship between Grade 12 students' aspirations and their perceived college readiness in the Philippines. The study found that students with higher aspirations for college also demonstrated higher levels of self-reported college readiness. This suggests a positive association between a strong desire for college and taking steps to prepare for it.

Table 5. *Relationship between Students Profile and College Readiness*

INDICATORS	PERSON R	P-VALUE	INTERPRETATION
SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP	-2E-16	0.18	SIGNIFICANT

Table 5 presents the relationship between the students' profile and their college readiness. As reflected in Table 4, the P-value is less than 0.5 therefore, the null hypothesis is being rejected and accepts the alternative hypothesis. This result implies that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and the respondents' level of college readiness.

This research findings imply a notable correlation between college preparedness and respondents' demographic characteristics, including age, gender and monthly income, aspiration and readiness.

This finding is supported by Gaertner and McClarty (2019) that factors like age, gender, track, and financial and study habits developed during middle school can influence college readiness later.

Conclusions

This study aimed to determine the level of college preparedness of grade 12 students at Mamali National High School. The study utilized a descriptive research design. The study's respondents consisted of 49 public senior high school students. An adopted survey questionnaire was administered to gather data from the respondents. Appropriate statistical tools were used to answer the research problem. The researchers collected the data themselves. The researchers analyzed the data using frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, and correlation.

Based on the study's collected data, the following findings are made: Of the 49 students, 38 were between the ages of 18 and 19, and 11 were over the age of 20. The gender survey of grade 12 students reveals that of the 49 students, 27 were male and 22 were female. The respondents track of grade 12 students shows that among the 49 students, in cooking, there are 18 and 15 students in GAS, while in ICT, there are 16 students. The respondents track of grade 12 students shows that among the 49 students, 6 students have a 30,000+ monthly financial income, 20 students have a monthly financial income of 29,999–20,000, and 23 students have a monthly financial income of 19,999 and below.

The survey results reveal the level of aspiration among grade 12 students at Mamali National High School to pursue a college degree. With a weighted mean of 1.14, Item No. 1 stands out as highly impacted, demonstrating students' determination to complete college despite facing various challenges. Item No. 13 received the lowest mean score of 2.94, indicating that students are confident in their academic abilities. The grand mean is 2.01, indicating a moderate degree of variation. The results indicate a moderate impact on the aspiration of Grade 12 students at Mamali National High School to pursue a college degree.

The readiness of grade 12 students at Mamali National High School to pursue a college degree is evident. The survey results clearly indicate the students' readiness to pursue a college degree. With a mean of 1.39, Item No. 1 has the highest weighted mean, indicating that students have clear college goals. Item no. 8's lowest weighted mean was 3.88, indicating that students are disciplined (if something needs to be done, I do it in a mannerly manner).

The grand mean is 2.42, which is slightly affected. The result shows that the Grade 12 students of Mamali National High School are slightly affected in their level of readiness to pursue a college degree.

Grade 12 senior high school students with Profile of Grade 12 students in College Preparedness among Grade 12 Students of Mamali National High School in terms of age, gender, track and average monthly financially income and level of aspiration and readiness in pursuing college degree. Therefore, when you correlate it Reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the Alternative Hypothesis which is there is a significant relationship between respondents' profile and respondents' level of college readiness.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Mae Ann N. Tolentino

Mamali National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Arsyl M. Andaya

Mamali National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Karen May P. Urlanda, EdD

Mamali National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Samantha R. Cuaresma

Mamali National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Vincent Roi B. Butalan

Mamali National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Matrex A. Mamintal

Mamali National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Christal Ashly Valdez

Mamali National High School
Department of Education – Philippines